

A Study to Assess the Level of Stress Among Nursing Students at Selected Nursing College, Puducherry

Jayanthi K ^{1*}, Dr. Renuka K ², Dr. Malliga M ³ and Dr. Shivasakthy M ⁴

¹PhD, Research Scholar, Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Puducherry, India.

*Corresponding Author Email: sanjayanthi1328@gmail.com

² Principal, College of Nursing, AIIMS, Gorakhpur & Guide, Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Puducherry, India.

³ Principal, Indirani College of Nursing & Co-Guide,

Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Puducherry, India.

⁴ Director, IHPE, Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth & Professor, Department of Prosthodontics, IGIDS & Co-Guide, Sri Balaji Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Puducherry, India.

Abstract

Background of the Study: Stress is the feeling of being under too much mental or emotional pressure. Pressure turns into stress when you feel unable to cope. People have different ways of reacting to stress, so a situation that feels stressful to one person may in fact be motivating to another. Many of life's demands can cause stress, especially work, relationships and money problems, and when you feel stressed, it can affect everything you do. Stress can affect how you feel, how you think, how you behave and how your body works. Sleeping problems, sweating, loss of appetite and difficulty concentrating are common signs of stress. Transition from secondary school to higher education is usually hard and demanding experience for students which lead to stress. **Objectives:** A study to assess the level of stress among nursing students. **Materials and Methods:** A descriptive design was chosen for the study to assess the level of stress among nursing students. A total of 60 nursing students were selected by simple random sampling technique using Lottery method was used, 60 B.sc nursing I year students were selected for the data collection procedure. The data collection was conducted among the 60 nursing students by using Perceived Stress scale. Level of stress was identified as mild, moderate, severe and very severe level of stress. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** In general, none of the nursing students are having mild-stress score. In 60 samples, level of stress among the nursing students' moderate level of stress were 24[40%], perceived severe level of stress among the nursing students were 35[58.3%]. Perceived very severe level of stress among the nursing students was 1[1.66%]. In this study, the highest score was severe level of stress was scored among nursing students. The level of stress had significant association chi-square value with demographic variables of Domicile [Urban and Rural], significant association level of stress among B.Sc. Nursing students with chi-square value of $x^2=8.9$, $df=3$ at $p > 0.05$ level. **Conclusion:** Assessing stress among Nursing students in colleges is important for the students' wellbeing and academic performance.

Keywords: Stress, Nursing Students and Nursing College.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is not itself an illness but it can cause serious illness if not tackled. It is important to recognize the symptoms of stress early. This will help you figure out ways of coping and save you from adopting unhealthy coping methods, such as drinking or smoking. Spotting the early signs of stress will also help prevent it worsening and potentially causing serious complications, such as high blood pressure, anxiety and depression.

Stress is the feeling of being under too much mental or emotional pressure. Pressure turns into stress when you feel unable to cope. People have different ways of reacting to stress, so a situation that feels stressful to one person may in fact be motivating to another. Many of life's demands can cause stress, especially work, relationships and money problems, and when you feel stressed, it can affect everything you do.

Stress can affect how you feel, how you think, how you behave and how your body works. Sleeping problems, sweating, loss of appetite and difficulty concentrating are common signs of stress. Transition from secondary school to higher education is usually hard and demanding experience for students which lead to stress.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Stress may affect the student's socialization, family relations, and performance at college, often with potentially serious long-term consequences. Adolescents with stress are at risk for increased hospitalizations, recurrent depressions, psychosocial impairment, alcohol abuse, and antisocial behaviors as they grow up.

Because the adolescent developmental period is so lengthy (10-12 years), it is usually broken down and discussed in terms of early, middle, and late adolescence. In fact, some developmental theorists even refer to yet another, separate developmental period between childhood and early teens calling these youth, "teens" or "teenagers" (between childhood and adolescence). Subsequently, today's youth face many challenges that are quite different from their parents' own teenage years; challenges that their parents simply did not encounter. Therefore, the parents of today's youth cannot readily draw upon their own teenage experiences to understand some of the difficulties facing youth in contemporary society.

While there is little you can do to prevent stress, there are many things you can do to manage stress more effectively, such as learning how to relax, taking regular exercise and adopting good time management techniques. However, a growing body of evidence has confirmed that adolescents not only experience the whole spectrum of mood disorders but also suffer from the significant morbidity and mortality associated with stress. This study aims to assess the level of stress among nursing students.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After obtaining permission from the Institutional Ethical Clearance and administrative officer from the Indirani College of Nursing and RAAK Nursing College. The researcher was given self-introduction and explanation about the study protocol to the samples. After that informed consent was obtained from the all samples. A quantitative descriptive research approach was adopted to assess the level of stress among nursing students. A descriptive design was chosen for the study to assess the level of stress among nursing students. Indirani College of Nursing and RAAK Nursing College, Puducherry, India served as the setting for the research study. A total of 60 nursing I year students who meets inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected for the data collection procedure by simple random sampling technique using Lottery method. The data collection instrument used in this study were demographic variable proforma, Perceived stress scale. The data collection was conducted among the 60 nursing students. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULTS

In general, none of the nursing students are having mild-stress score. In 60 samples, level of stress among the nursing students’ moderate level of stress were 24[40%], perceived severe level of stress among the nursing students were 35[58.3%]. Perceived very severe level of stress among the nursing students was 1[1.66%]. In this study, the highest score was severe level of stress was scored among nursing students. The level of stress had significant association chi-square value with demographic variables of Domicile [Urban And Rural], significant association level of stress among BSc Nursing students with chi- square value of $\chi^2=8.9$, $df=3$ at $p > 0.05$ level.

Table 1: Distribution of Nursing Students According to their Level of Stress N=60

S.No	Stress Level	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Mild Stress	0	0
2	Moderate Stress	24	40
3	Severe Stress	35	58.33
4	Very Severe Stress	1	1.66
	Total	60	100

Fig 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Nursing Students According to their Level of Stress

The above table and figure shows that according to their level of stress 0 (0%) students had low level stress, 24(40%) students had moderate level stress, 35(58.33%) students had severe level stress and 1(1.66%) student had very severe level of stress.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

The purpose of this to assess the level of stress among the nursing students at selected nursing colleges, Puducherry.

In general, none of the nursing students are having mild-stress score. In 60 samples, level of stress among the nursing students’ moderate level of stress were 24[40%], severe level of stress among the nursing students were 35[58.3%]. very severe level of stress among the nursing students

was 1[1.66%]. In this study, the highest score was severe level of stress was scored among nursing students.

The finding of the study is supported by the researcher conducted by B. Verma et.al (2016) Psychological stress among students in Gandhi Nagar, Gujarat, India. score: 15-30: experiencing a little pressure but generally feels in control (Low Stress), 31-45: good level of control most of the time. Situations cause stress occasionally (Moderate Stress), 46- 60: often feel under pressure and out of control (High Stress), 61-75: high level of pressure and feel out of control (Extreme High Stress). Almost 85% of participants have high stress, 13% moderate stress and 2% of participants have extremely high stress.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the level of stress among the nursing students at selected nursing colleges, Puducherry was high and they need to be taken into care with psychological support.

Implication

The study findings were beneficial in the following ways: Teachers have to take up the responsibilities to plan teaching programme on stress management to students. Nursing curriculum should reinforce on the knowledge regarding the stress management to students. Administrators should plan and organize the stress management sessions periodically for the students in order to reduce their stress and improve wellbeing.

Conflict of Interest: No

References

- 1) Kploanyi, E. E., Dwomoh, D., & Dzodzomenyo, M. (2020). The effect of occupational stress on depression and insomnia: a cross-sectional study among employees in a Ghanaian telecommunication company. *BMC public health*, 20(1), 1-10.
- 2) Zerbini, G., Ebigbo, et al., (2020). Psychosocial burden of healthcare professionals in times of COVID-19—a survey conducted at the University Hospital Augsburg. *GMS German Medical Science*, 18.
- 3) Soteriades, E. S., Psalta, L., Leka, et al., (2019). Occupational stress and musculoskeletal symptoms in firefighters. *International journal of occupational medicine and environmental health*, 32(3), 341-352.
- 4) Miyoshi, Y. (2019). Restorative yoga for occupational stress among Japanese female nurses working night shift: Randomized crossover trial. *Journal of occupational health*, 61(6), 508-516.
- 5) Bostock, S., Crosswell, A. D., Prather, et al., (2019). Mindfulness on-the-go: Effects of a mindfulness meditation app on work stress and well-being. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 24(1), 127.
- 6) Prasad, K. D. V., Vaidya, R., & Anil Kumar, V. (2018). Association among occupational stress factors and performance at workplace among agricultural research sector employees at hyderabad, India. *Pacific Business Review International (TSI)*, 10(7), 27-36.
- 7) Choy, H. B., & Wong, M. C. (2017). Occupational stress and burnout among Hong Kong dentists. *Hong Kong Med J*, 23(5), 480-488.

- 8) Rajesh, A., & Kumar, M. P. S. (2016). Occupational Stress among School Teachers—A Study Report. *St. Theresa Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1).
- 9) Della Valle, E., Palermi, S., Aloe, et al., (2020). Effectiveness of workplace yoga interventions to reduce perceived stress in employees: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Functional Morphology and Kinesiology*, 5(2), 33.
- 10) Witmer, B. G., & Singer, M. J. (1998). Measuring presence in virtual environments: A presence questionnaire. *Presence*, 7(3), 225-240.
- 11) Silva-Júnior, F. L., Emanuel, P., Sousa, J et al., (2016). Prior acute mental exertion in exercise and sport. *Clinical practice and epidemiology in mental health: CP & EMH*, 12, 94.
- 12) Leung, M. Y., Liang, Q., & Yu, J. (2016). Development of a mindfulness–stress–performance model for construction workers. *Construction Management and Economics*, 34(2), 110-128.